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Human Resource Management Practices: A Case Study of Confifi Group of Hotels in Sri Lanka

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Abstract In contemporary management practices, Human Resource Management (HRM) is considered as one of the key contributing factors to the success of the organizations at present. Further, companies are now putting a greater emphasis on managing HRM policies and practices to gain a competitive advantage and eventually to position their value proposition in a lucrative manner. Particularly this case study has paid much attention on more than a few HRM practices of Confifi Group of Hotels. Some of the HRM practices include terms and conditions, job design, recruitment and selection, human resource planning, training and development, quality issues, communication and consultation, promotions and evaluations and pay system. In the last part of this paper some recommendations are provided for Confifi Group to gain competitive advantages through HRM practices.

Key words: Competitive Advantage, HRM Practices, Human Resource Management, Organizations.

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1. Introduction

For a country like Sri Lanka, eventual purpose of a nation is enhanced standard of living of its people, (Opatha, 2009). Given that, Human Resource Management (HRM) practices are considered as a tool for achieving competitive advantage due to the capability to convert the other resources (money, machine, methods and material) in to output (product/service), (Tiwari & Saxena, 2012, and Islam, 2006 cited in . At past there was no identity for individuals in the perspective of HRM, and HRM was not considered as a part of the administration functions of the organization.

2. Literature Review

Literature proliferates with definitions most of which are in consonant with each other on what Human Resource(s) Management (HRM) means in general. At present HRM can be identified as a very significant field of Organizational Management, (Opatha, 2009). Adding to that, HRM is deals with management of Human Resources in an organization. Besides, Tiwari & Saxena, (2012), perceived as the source of achieving competitive advantage because of its capability to convert the other resources (money, machine, methods and material) in to output (product/service). Further they postulated that other resources other than human resource are can be imitated by competitors. The significance of people resourcing is affirmed by Barney, (1991); Lado and Wilson, (1994), suggesting that managing people is more difficult than managing technology or capital. Tiwari & Saxena, (2012), suggested a notion called Human Resource Management Systems in order to an implementation of effective management of human resource. Moreover, it is indispensable to have effective human resource management functions to develop a sound HRM system, (Tiwari & Saxena, 2012). Wright & Snell, (1991) defines HRM practices refers to organizational activities directed at managing the pool of human resource and ensuring that

the resources are employed towards the fulfillment of organizational goals. Nonetheless, HRM practices are not identical; those can be differing from organization to organization and country to country, (Tiwari & Saxena, 2012).

Besides, Chandler & McEvoy (2000), postulated an argument raising that one of the lingering questions in HRM research is whether or not there is a single set of policies or practices that represents a 'universally superior approach' to managing people. However, several attempts have been made in order to identify types of HRM practices in different sectors in the world, (Tiwari & Saxena, 2012). Most notably, Pfeffer (1994) identified 16 HRM practices which denote best practices. Later this was refined to these HRM practices namely, Employment security, Selective hiring, Self-managed teams/team working, High compensation contingent on organizational

Performance, Extensive training, Reduction in status difference, and Sharing information, (Tiwari & Saxena, 2012). Apart from that, Redman and Matthews (1998) identified a concept called a 'HRM bundle'. They affirmed that, the bundle consists with best practices which are supporting for service organizations quality strategies. These being, Careful recruitment and selection, Extensive remuneration systems, Team working and flexible job design, Training and learning, Employee involvement, and Performance appraisals. As per the recent studies, Saxena and Tiwari (2009), acknowledged Training and Development, Employer- Employee Relations, Recognition through Rewards, Culture building, Career Development, Compensation and Benefits as important HRM Practices.

3. Research Methodology

Mainly this article is case study based, written in an exploratory manner. Besides, the motivation is to select the Confifi Group is the group is one of the largest hotel chains in Sri Lanka. And the recent acquisition valued around Rs 900mn. The Confifi Group of

Companies is currently having a separate human resource department and all functions are being practiced with the authority of the Group Human Resource Development Manager (GHRDM). Face to face interviews with the GHRMD is the major part of this case study, using a questionnaire, which consists of view and opinions of the interviewed party, which might raise the question of bias. In some cases some of them were not able to provide concrete facts or figures. In this case some assumptions had to be made. Interviewing the GHRMD is the primary source of data gathering in this case study. Furthermore, company brochures, documents, and the company website were the secondary sources of data. No survey method has been used in this regard. The advantage of the case study over other methods is that it attempts to be comprehensive, and involves the researcher in describing and analyzing the full notes, (Tiwari & Saxena, 2012). The case study method has further affirmed by Mitchell (1999) stating that the basic problem in the use of case material is theoretical analysis. Nonetheless, a single case study can give a lot of depth in the research area Mellahi, Jackson & Sparks, 2002).

4. Confifi Group of Hotels - Company Overview

The Confifi Group (100% domestic) established in 1969 owns and manages 3 popular beach holiday resorts on the south west coast of Sri Lanka in Beruwala catering to a wide range of holiday preferences from a beach resort. The 5-star Eden Resort & Spa offers a private, exclusive environment, the 4-star Riverina with its spacious rooms is a favourite with families with children and the 3-star Club Palm Garden offers exciting animation to those who like to be active even on holidays.

The Confifi Group of Hotels is the only chain amongst beach resorts in Sri Lanka to offer a choice of Wellness in its resorts. The Eden Resort with its Aromatherapy Spa, the Riverina Hotel and its authentic Ayurveda Villa including a qualified Ayurveda physician, and the

Club Palm Garden with a traditional Thai Centre with professional therapists from Thailand. A unique facility our guests are entitled to is access to each others Wellness Centers, Horse Riding, and Biking. The Riverina Hotel and Club Palm Garden are located on one large expanse of beach front and the Eden is just a 2-minute walk along the beach.

Since all these three hotels are under the Confifi Group, HR Section is controlled by the Group Human Resource & Development Manager (GHRDM). For each hotel there is an Asst. HR Manager, who mainly deals with operational activities but the GHRDM is involved in functional activities and he involves in operational activities in an advisory or consulting capacity. Under the Asst. HR Manager there is an HR executive and two assistants.

Recently a major change in the Confifi group was incorporated with the acquisition of the group by Lanka Orix Leasing Company (LOLC) and the transactions were executed through the Colombo Stock Exchange (CSE) and valued over 900mn. *(See Appendix 01-The new holding structure of Confifi Group)*

HR processes and practices are also common to all three hotels. Most of the HR functions are performed at the hotel itself and only recommendations are delivered from the Head Office. Basically there are no officers to be seen in the organization hierarchy, who report to the GHRDM. In the structure it looks like HR Departments of the hotels are functioning independently but generally recommendations and approvals are sought from the head office for the hotel HR Department's actions. *(See Appendix 02- Organization Structure of Confifi Group)*

4.1. Eden Resort & spa

Eden Resort & Spa is the most valuable, first-class and only 5 star hotel in Confifi group. It was established 15 years before in Beruwala which falls into the category of Greater Colombo. The total number of room at Eden is 158 which are catagorised as follows.

1. Eden Rooms-113 rooms having both sea and land views; majority are sea facing.
2. Superior Rooms-23 spacious rooms all located on the ground floor, opening direct into a private terrace, garden and pool.
3. Paradise Rooms-16 deluxe elegantly furnished rooms all sea-facing and with private check-in / check-out facilities.
4. Paradise Suites-4 spacious suites with separate sitting and bedrooms, in-room dining facility, larger balcony and Jacuzzi in the bathroom.
5. Penthouses-2 elegant rooftop Penthouses with stunning views over the ocean, private timber sundeck and private outdoor dining.

Number of full time employees working at Eden are 77 and other than them there are 173 contract employees, 14 trainees and 25 executives.

4.2. Riverina Hotel

Riverina is the 4-star hotel in the Confifi Group, which is situated in Beruwala, falling into the category of south coast. It is the second best hotel in the group which was established before 15 years.

The hotel is comprised of 192 tastefully furnished rooms and 03 suites, a choice of three (03) restaurants (coffee shop, international buffet, Beach Restaurant), three (03) bars and discotheque, Ayurveda Villa, gymnasium and many more luxurious facilities. Number of full

time employees at Riverina are 98 with 148 contract employees, 14 casual employees, 39 trainees and 33 executives.

4.3. Club Palm Gardens

Club Palm Gardens, which is the three star hotel in the group falls into the category of South Coast. It is comprised of 142 attractively furnished rooms, Main dining restaurant, Two (02) bars, Sports facilities, Gymnasium etc.

The total number of employees of the hotel is less than the other two hotels. There are 50 full time employees, 87 contract employees, 5 casual employees, 20 trainees and 22 executives working at the hotel.

5. HR Practices of Confifi Group

Since all three hotels are under the common control of Confifi, we considered only the common process of the group. HR Divisions of the three hotels are functionally controlled by GHRDM but they are given freedom to carry out operations on their own. Major operational activities of HR like recruitment, selection are done by hotels separately but approvals and recommendations for them are obtained from GHRDM. It is easy to get an understanding about the processes when we take them up separately.

5.1. Terms and Conditions

Mainly hotel's staff is divided into two categories as Executives and Non Executives. Executives are comprised of Managers and Supervisors where Non Executives are comprised of Entry Level Staff. (Room boys, waiters etc.) According to the discussion held with Mr. Nishantha Jayasinghe who is the Group Human Resource & Development Manager (GHRDM), there are many activities in the hotel to build good relationship among employees. Each hotel has a Welfare Society which is chaired by a worker where the

Residence Manager involves in its activities in an advisory capacity. Annual staff trip, Confifi talent development program, Inter group competitions are some of the activities organized by the Welfare Society. These activities are funded by the hotel where all levels of staff participate in the events.

When it comes to recruitment, Confifi does not maintain a policy of recruiting only males or unmarried males. If the candidate fulfills the requirements, he or she will be hired for the post. But because of the nature of the industry hotels are reluctant to hire women or married persons. GHRDM explained us certain occasions where the CVs of girls were rejected because their stay in the hotel after marriage was doubtful. Therefore Confifi is more into hiring boys than girls.

When filling a vacancy, internal employees are given the priority. But GHRDM stated that there are no competent employees in lower levels to fill higher level positions. As a result vacancies of executives are filled externally.

Confifi, as a practice recruit only 80% of the labour requirement. During the season (i.e. from August to April) the deficit of 20% is filled by making the existing employees to work overtime, recruiting contract employees etc. As a result there will not be excess employees during the off season. Therefore the problem of redundancy is not an issue to Confifi.

5.2. Recruitment and Selection

Recruitment is basically done by the HR department of the relevant hotel but the approval and recommendation for recruitment is given by GHRDM. *(See Appendix 03-Recruitment Process of Confifi Group)*

When it comes to recruiting executives, Confifi is more interested in recruiting executives with experience in the industry. The hotel is not very much worried whether entry level staff

have experience or not, but they should have the minimum qualifications for the post and prove in the interview that they are in the capacity to absorb the training given after they are recruited. The hotel has the attitude that such raw entry level staff can be moulded and trained the way hotel wants.

Attitude or psychological test is not held when recruiting. But after they are recruited, on going employee satisfaction surveys and attitude tests are carried out by an officer called 'Duty Manager'. These survey results are used when planning training programs and employee evaluations. This is also used as a tool of understanding the requirements of employees and attitude development

When recruiting entry level staff, hotel looks for employees who have multi skills but not necessarily. Because Confifi gives only a specific task to the employee and does not shift him to another job. Realistic job previews are not being seen during recruitment instead interviews are held in traditional way.

When new employees are recruited an induction program is held. This is held monthly for new batches. In that program general understanding of the industry, job specification, targets etc. are given to new recruits.

5.3. *Human Resource Planning*

Though there is a formalized business plan (BP) for every 5 years, a formalized HR plan which is linked to BP is not to be seen. All HR activities are done on estimates and not properly validated.

Even though there are many training programs and activities held for employees, a formalized career development plan is not in action. An employee, who joins as a room boy remains in his position even after 10-15 years, gives evidence that there is no career plan.

And also we observed a letter written by a supervisor asking the GHRDM to demote him to his previous position. This proves that employees' career is not developed in a way to accept responsibilities.

5.4. Training

A formal and documented training & development program is conducted by the GHRDM for the employees of three hotels. Training is conducted, basically categorizing employees into three layers. They are Entry Level, Supervisors and Managers. The training programs for each category are different from one another. A monthly training need analysis (TNA) which is prepared by GHRDM is based on Guest Satisfaction Index (GSI) which is a summarized report prepared from the Guest Satisfaction forms filled by guests. Evaluation Reports from the department heads are also considered when preparing TNA. (*See Appendix 04-Training Process*)

There are lots of ways of giving training to employees. Most occasions on the job training is given with the supervision and guidance his immediate supervisor. In addition technical training for department heads, supplier introductions for liquor bar staff, abroad training for kitchen staff are the common training methods applied at Confifi. All staff members are allowed to browse internet, where they get the chance to browse to get additional knowledge and training.

Though there are many training programs held in the hotel, none of them are compulsory for employees. They are not forced to participate in trainings, instead they have the choice to participate or not.

5.5. *Job Design*

At Confifi employees are given specific tasks. They are not rotated from one job to another. But very rarely line work rotation is applied. Therefore an employee, who joined the hotel as a waiter, is a waiter forever. He does not get a chance to get the exposure on overall operations of the hotel.

When it comes to minor staff, their jobs are designed in such a manner to get the work of the hotel done. Without considering internal skills of the employee their jobs are designed. But it is different when it comes to executive posts. Since they join the hotel with industry knowledge and professional qualifications, their job is designed in order to make full use of employee's skills and abilities.

Normally employees are given targets as groups as well as individually. A room boy might be given a target take care of 10-15 rooms at the same time. Each hotel is given targets to attract a particular number of customers for a month. Then all the staff at the hotel work together as a group to achieve the target.

As a general practice of the hotel, managerial level staff prepares plans and targets for the entire organization and lower level employees' task is to implement them. No formal feedback is taken from them, regarding the difficulties faced when implementing plans. Duty Managers are the persons who monitor employees' performance.

5.6. *Quality Issues*

Improving and maintaining the quality of the service provided, is a major concern of the hotel. Each employee is responsible for the quality issues of his service. If we take a room boy, he is responsible for the quality for his daily work, cleaning supervisor (his immediate supervisor) is responsible for his monthly work and finally General Manager is responsible

for his annual work. That is the procedure adopted by the hotel to maintain the overall quality of the work.

Quality circles or quality managers are not seen at Confifi. Guest Satisfaction Index (GSI) is the main quality controller. When customers leave the hotel after their stay, a GSI form is given to them to fill. It covers all service areas of the hotel and the customer ranks them according to his satisfaction level. These results are monitored by the General Manager and based on results a summarized report is prepared and sent to the GHRDM. Through GHRDM, the director board takes necessary actions to improve quality.

5.7. Communication & Consultation

Ongoing attitude survey of employees is done by the officers called 'Duty Managers'. They move with the employees and get the feedback from them regarding the working environment, attitudes and problems and report the results to the management.

An ongoing briefing of lower level employees' duties by their supervisors is not being seen in the hotel. Instead an overall understanding of their job (Job Description) is given during induction or other training sessions. At the same time targets, goals of the employees are also given. But for the lower level staff, knowledge on market position, competitive pressure etc. is not given.

5.8. Promotions & Evaluations

Confifi carries out evaluations on employees every six months. This evaluation is done by the relevant department head and the recommendation is submitted to the GHRDM. In the evaluation report, the department head recommends the employee a promotion, salary increment or both. Based on his recommendation GHRDM takes necessary decisions on the

employee. Employee's acceptance on his evaluation is also attached along with the evaluation report.

5.9. Pay System

The pay system of the employees is based on two methods. One is paying the salary the employee demands and the other is paying market rates. If the employee has fulfilled all requirements and has required qualifications, the hotel will pay the salary he demands. If the employee is willing to work at the industry rates, he will be paid the industry rates. Within the organization, the pay structure is based on employees' level of responsibility. Compulsory payments stipulated by law (EPF, ETF, Gratuity) are being paid properly.

6. Concluding Remarks

The selected three hotels are of different nature. The Confifi group, which has three hotels namely Club Palm Gardens, Riverina, Eden Resort have three levels in the industry. When compared with other hotels in the industry, Confifi has a good HR process. The training and evaluation method which is mainly handled by the GHRDM is very effective for employees' carrier. A great attention is paid on employees and periodically their attitudes are tested and the feedback is taken from them. There are many activities in the hotel to improve relationship among employees.

Even though there are activities to maintain relationship among employees, a clear hierarchical difference is seen in the hotel as the executives and non executives are treated in different ways. On the other hand if a room boy is hired he will be a room boy forever and lower level employees are reluctant to take up responsibilities. There is no concern in the hotel to investigate on the reasons for them and also we can say that the training sessions that

are organized for them are also not effective. But when it is taken as a whole Confifi is on a better position in HR.

In other two hotels, Goldi Sands and Pegasus Reef the practices and processes are same as Confifi. But the HR sections are not that much sophisticated as Confifi. Since Pegasus is a member of a foreign group, abroad training, application of foreign HR practices are to be seen. But the weakness in Pegasus is that it emphasizes experience of the employee rather than training and the jobs are specific. But cross functional promotions, abroad training is being seen.

When it comes to Goldi Sands a formal HR division is not seen and employee satisfaction is also not surveyed. As the conclusion we can categorize Confifi as the best out of others and Pegasus is also up to some standard than Goldi Sands. But all three hotels show common features in the hotel industry.

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Appendix: 01**The new holding structure of the Confifi Group**

Appendix 03

Recruitment & Selection Process of Confifi Group

Appendix 04

Training & Development Process of Confifi Group

